

CORRELATION AND PATH ANALYSIS STUDIES IN DESI COTTON [*Gossypium arboreum* L.]D.B. Pawar^{*1}, Dr. A. H. Rathod², Dr. S. B. Borgaonkar³ and Dr. D. K. Zate⁴^{*1}M.Sc. students, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.² Assistant Breeder, Breeder Seed Production Unit, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.³ Cotton Breeder, Cotton Research Station, MB Farm, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.⁴ Assistant Professor, Department of Agril Botany, College of Agriculture, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.

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MS Received: 10.11.2024; MS Revised: 21.12.2024; MS Accepted: 22.12.2024

MS 3322

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURE)

Abstract

This investigation aimed to analyze correlations and conduct path analysis studies in desi cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.). Thirty-two diverse elite cotton genotypes, including two check varieties, were cultivated in a randomized block design with two replications during the 2023-24 kharif season at the Cotton Research Station, Mahboob Baugh Farm, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani. Correlation coefficients played a pivotal role in elucidating trait associations, with genotypic correlation generally surpassing phenotypic correlation, revealing inherent trait relationships. This understanding is crucial for crop enhancement programs, offering insights into the relative contributions of each trait to overall yield. Correlation analysis revealed significant positive genotypic and phenotypic correlations between plant height, number of bolls per plant and seed cotton yield per plant. Path coefficient analysis determined direct and indirect trait effects on seed cotton yield per plant, emphasizing traits such as the plant height, number of bolls per plant and uniformity ratio which directly and positively impacted yield. The study underscored that the number of bolls per plant, plant height, boll weight, number of sympodia per plant, ginning percentage and fibre fineness were pivotal for effectively selecting superior desi cotton genotypes.

Key words- Desi Cotton, Correlation, Path Coefficient Analysis, Correlation Coefficient

Introduction

Cotton is an important crop for sustainable economy of India and livelihood of the Indian Cotton Farming Community. Cotton was first cultivated as a fabric in the Indus River valley about 3000 B.C., now it is grown all over the world, mainly for its fibre. Often it is referred to as "White Gold" or King of fibre crop for its global importance and industrial utility (Romeu-Dalmau *et al.*, 2015). As it is the world's most important non-food agricultural commodity, it is essential input for textile production, which provides raw material to cotton textile industries. Presently nearly 60 million people depend directly or indirectly on cotton in various activities like cultivation, marketing, processing and export for their livelihood (Wendel *et al.*, 2012). Among the 50 species of cotton, which are the world's most important crop for fiber, 44 are diploid ($2n=2x=26$) and remaining species are allotetraploids ($2n=4x=52$). There is total four cultivated species of cotton among these; diploid species (*G. arboreum* L. and *G. herbaceum* L.) are known as old world cotton and tetraploid (*G. hirsutum* L. and *G. barbadense* L.) as new world cotton which are grown commercially in India (Koebnick *et al.*, 2019). Cotton seed had gained the additional economic importance as a major contributor to edible oil, protein and other by-products (Hasan & Latha, 2017). Correlation studies offer a greater understanding of the relationship that exists between highly heritable characteristics and most economic characters, as well as a better comprehension of the contribution of each variable to the genetic makeup of the crop (Singh *et al.*, 2018). Since seed cotton yield and fiber quality traits are complex quantitative traits influenced by environmental factors, direct selection may not always be a reliable approach. Breeders must consider both the direct

and indirect effects of various traits when making selection decisions (Jangid *et al.*, 2022).

Path coefficient analysis is an effective tool for partitioning correlations into direct and indirect effects, aiding in the selection of traits. A deeper understanding of the traits influencing yield, along with their direct and indirect relationships, is essential for designing efficient breeding programs ((Jangid *et al.*, 2022).

Material And Method

Thirty-two accessions of *desi* cotton were used for characterization, correlation and path analysis studies in randomized block design with two replications during *kharif* 2023-2024. Plot size of *desi* cotton was 0.9×4.5 m² with spacing of 45 cm \times 22.5 cm. All recommended package of practices were followed as suitable for the climate conditions of Parbhani. Data was recorded on five randomly tagged plants for viz., days to 50 per cent flowering, number of monopodia, number of sympodia, plant height, number of bolls per plant, boll weight, ginning percentage, uniformity ratio, fiber strength, upper half mean length, micronaire, and seed cotton yield per plant. In general, genotypic correlation was larger than phenotypic correlation, owing to the relative contribution of genetic factors in genotypes, as most of them had undergone some kind of selection (Johnson *et al.* (1995). Direct effect on seed cotton yield of any trait gives idea about reliability of indirect selections to be done through that trait brings about increase in seed cotton yield. If direct effects as well as correlation are high and significant then correlation describes its true relationship and selections would be effective for that character. The two standard checks included PA-740 and PA- 810 obtained from Cotton Research Station, Mahboob Baugh Farm, Parbhani.

Table 1: Experiment material

	Genotypes	Source
1	NDLA 3133	ARS, Nandyal
2	DAS 1202	UAS, Dharwad
3	GAM 223	JAU, Amreli
4	CAN 2030	CICR, Nagpur
5	PBD 22	PAU, Bhatinda
6	KWA 1301	CRS, Khandwa
7	GAM 259	JAU, Amreli
8	MDL 2663	CRS Madchal
9	HD 550	CRS, Hissar
10	GAM 360	JAU, Amreli
11	DWDA 1301	UAS, Dharwad
12	FDK 2811	PAU Faridkot

13	CNA 1036	CICR, Nagpur
14	NDLA 266	ARS, Nandyal
15	NDLA 3115	ARS, Nandyal
16	PA 740 (C)	CRSMB VNMKV, Parbhani
17	FDK 286	PAU Faridkot
18	RG 784	MPKV, Rahuri
19	DWDA 1702	UAS, Dharwad
20	CAN 1016	CICR, Nagpur
21	GAM 236	JAU, Amreli
22	CNA 1638	CICR, Nagpur
23	CNA 1032	CICR, Nagpur
24	GAM 255	JAU Amreli
25	UAS 752	UAS Dharwad
26	NDLA 3116	ARS, Nandyal
27	RG 776	MPKV, Rahuri
28	PBD 35	PAU, Bhatinda
29	JLA 1261	CRS, Jalgaon
30	CISA 405	CRS Sirsa Haryana
31	NDLA 2661	ARS, Nandyal
32	PA 810 (C)	CRSMB VNMKV, Parbhani

Result And Discussion

Correlation studies were conducted on 32 different cotton genotypes to investigate the interrelationships between various yield components at both genotypic (G) and phenotypic (P) levels. The results of the genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficients for 12 characters are presented in Table 2. The characters at both genotypic and phenotypic level showed that plant height and number of bolls per plant were positively correlated with seed cotton yield per plant. Days to 50% flowering, Number of monopodia, ginning percentage and fiber strength showed negative correlation with seed cotton yield per plant at both genotypic and phenotypic level as shown in Fig. 1 Similar results were reported by Pinki *et al.*, (2018) in American cotton, Nawaz *et al.*, (2019) in American cotton, Satish *et al.* (2020) in American cotton, Sangwan *et al.*, (2023) in desi cotton, Nikhil *et al.*, (2023) in American cotton and Sukrutha *et al.*, (2024) in desi cotton.

Days to 50 % flowering showed positive and significant correlation with fiber strength. Similar results were reported Similar result finding was reported by Sahar *et al.*, (2021) in American cotton. Boll weight showed positive and significant correlation with fiber strength and similar results obtained by by Nawaz *et al.*, (2019) in American cotton, Chapepa *et al.*, (2020), Gnanasekaran *et al.*, (2020) and Bhatti *et al.*, (2020) in American cotton. Uniformity ratio exhibited positive and significant correlation with upper half mean length. The similar results were also reported by Sahar *et al.*, (2021) in American cotton, Patankar (2021) in American cotton and Jangid *et al.*, (2022) in desi cotton. Fiber strength exhibited positive and significant correlation with upper half mean length. Similar kind of results were reported by Patil *et al.*, (2022) in American cotton, Sangwan *et al.*, (2023) in desi cotton and Nidagundi *et al.*, (2023) in American cotton. This finding holds significant importance for breeders because it suggests that component breeding could be highly effective in this context.

Path analysis between yield, yield contributing and fiber quality characters were carried out to find the direct and indirect effect from given component characters on seed cotton yield. Path coefficient analysis was worked out for twelve different characters at both genotypic and phenotypic level. The results are presented in Table 3. Days to 50 percent flowering exhibited direct negative effect (-0.1926) on seed cotton yield per plant. It has negative indirect effect through boll weight (-0.0098) followed by ginning percent (-0.0901), uniformity ratio (-0.0297), fiber strength (-0.0723), upper half mean length (-0.0355), number of sympodia per plant (-0.0058), upper half mean length (0.0027) and fiber strength (-0.0012) on seed cotton yield per plant. While, positive indirect effect was recorded for number of monopodia (0.0525), number of sympodia (0.0245), plant height (0.0032), number of bolls (0.0731) on seed cotton yield per plant at

genotypical level. These results were in agreement with the findings of Chapepa *et al.*, (2020) and Arunkumar and Murthy (2020) in American cotton. Plant height exhibited direct effect (0.7810) on seed cotton yield per plant. These results are in accordance with the findings of Sukrutha *et al.*, (2024) in desi cotton. Number of monopodia per plant exhibited negative direct effect (-0.2645) on seed cotton yield per plant. These results are in confirmation with the findings of Sahar *et al.*, (2021) in American cotton and Jangid *et al.*, (2022) in desi cotton. Number of sympodia per plant exhibited negative direct effect (-0.0541) on seed cotton yield per plant. Similar kind of results were confirmed by of Patil *et al.*, (2022) and Nidagundi *et al.*, (2023) in American cotton, and Sangwan *et al.*, (2023) in desi cotton.

Number of bolls per plant exhibited highly positive direct effect (0.1352) on seed cotton yield per plant. These results are in conformity with the results reported by Sukrutha *et al.*, (2024) in desi cotton. Boll weight exhibited direct negative effect (-0.6203) on seed cotton yield per and the traits *viz.*, number of monopodia (0.2033), number of sympodia (0.3478), number of bolls (0.0028), ginning percent (0.2306), uniformity ratio (0.0282) showed positive indirect effect on seed cotton yield per plant. Ginning percent exhibited negative direct effect (-0.4870) on seed cotton yield per plant and negative indirect effect was recorded through days to 50 % flowering (-0.2279), number of monopodia (-0.2013), plant height (-0.0038), fiber strength (-0.0329) and micronaire (-0.1266). These results confirmed the findings of Chinchane *et al.* (2021) in desi cotton, Patil *et al.*, (2022) in American cotton and Sangwan *et al.*, (2023) in desi cotton. Upper half mean length exhibited negative direct effect (-0.7365) on seed cotton yield per plant and it had shown positive indirect effect through number of monopodia (0.0221), number of sympodia (0.1713), plant height (0.0089), number of bolls (0.1893), ginning percentage (0.2105) and micronaire (0.4286). These results were agreements with Sangwan *et al.*, (2023) in desi cotton. Fiber strength exhibited positive direct effect (0.3610) on seed cotton yield per plant. These results were agreements with Sangwan *et al.*, (2023) in desi cotton and Nidagundi *et al.*, (2023) in American cotton. The fiber fineness exhibited direct effect (0.0112) on seed cotton yield per plant. These results were agreements with Sukrutha *et al.*, (2024) in desi cotton. The uniformity ratio exhibited positive direct effect (0.1285) on seed cotton yield per plant. These results were agreements with Nidagundi *et al.*, (2023) in American cotton. The path coefficient analysis conducted in our current study highlighted the significance of several traits, including the plant height, number of bolls per plant, boll weight in breeding for higher seed cotton yield per plant.

Table 2: Genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficient analysis for morphological, yield contributing and fibre characters in cotton.

Characters		Days to 50 % flowering	Number of monopodia	Number of sympodia	Plant height (cm)	Number of bolls/plant	Boll weight (g)	Ginning (%)	Uniformity ratio (%)	Fiber strength (g/tex)	Upper half mean length (mm)	Micronaire (µg/inch)	Seed cotton yield/plant (g)
Days to 50 % flowering	G	1.000	-0.272*	-0.127	-0.017	-0.380**	0.051	0.468**	0.154	0.375 **	0.184	-0.254 *	-0.421**
	P	1.000	-0.178	-0.059	0.001	-0.267*	0.028	0.201	0.124	0.347**	0.153	-0.143	-0.304*
Number of monopodia	G		1.000	-0.042	0.025	-0.126	-0.328**	0.650**	0.039	-0.010	-0.030	0.220	-0.295*
	P		1.000	-0.066	0.010	-0.129	-0.116	0.178	0.058	-0.005	-0.046	0.182	-0.156
Number of sympodia	G			1.000	-0.204	0.691*	-0.561**	0.413**	-0.260*	-0.125	-0.233	0.182	0.157
	P			1.000	-0.162	0.585**	-0.381**	0.176	-0.241	-0.072	-0.0200	0.221	0.0141
Plant height (cm)	G				1.000	0.189	0.648**	0.008	-0.095	0.380**	-0.012	0.038	0.543**
	P				1.000	0.159	0.555**	0.025	0.068	0.375**	-0.010	0.047	0.441**
Number of bolls/plant	G					1.000	-0.005	-0.015	-0.340**	-0.062	-0.257*	0.366**	0.490**
	P					1.000	0.008	-0.015	-0.342**	-0.070	-0.240	0.283*	0.482**
Boll weight (g)	G						1.000	-0.372**	-0.045	0.347**	0.065	0.096	0.246
	P						1.000	-0.202	-0.075	0.312*	0.067	0.089	0.250*
Ginning (%)	G							1.000	-0.107	0.067	-0.286*	0.260*	-0.313*
	P							1.000	-0.065	0.021	-0.150	0.014	-0.229
Uniformity ratio (%)	G								1.000	0.526**	0.801**	-0.582**	-0.344**
	P								1.000	0.486**	0.714**	-0.423**	-0.350**
Fiber Strength (g/tex)	G									1.0000	0.700**	-0.228	-0.112
	P									1.0000	0.649**	-0.163	-0.098
Upper half mean length (mm)	G										1.0000	-0.582**	-0.348**
	P										1.0000	-0.541**	-0.293*
Micronaire (µg/inch)	G											1.0000	0.156
	P											1.0000	0.082
Seed Cotton yield /plant (g)	G												1.0000
	P												1.0000

*Significant at 5 per cent level, **Significant at 1 per cent level

Table 3: Genotypic path coefficient analysis for morphological, yield contributing and fibre characters in cotton

Sr no.	Characters	Days to 50 % flowering	Number of monopodia	Number of Sympodia	Plant height (cm)	Number of bolls/plant	Boll Weight (g)	Ginning percentage (%)	Uniformity Ratio (%)	Fiber Strength (g/tex)	Upper Half Mean Length (mm)	Micronaire ($\mu\text{g}/\text{inch}$)
1	Days to 50 % flowering	-0.1926	0.0525	0.0245	0.0032	0.0731	-0.0098	-0.0901	-0.0297	-0.0723	-0.0355	0.0490
2	Number of monopodia	0.0720	-0.2645	0.0111	-0.0066	0.0334	0.0867	-0.1719	-0.0103	0.0028	0.0079	-0.0582
3	Number of Sympodia	-0.0069	0.0023	-0.0541	0.0110	-0.0374	0.0303	-0.0224	0.0141	0.0068	0.0126	-0.0098
4	Plant height (cm)	-0.0131	0.0194	-0.1590	0.7810	0.1477	0.5060	0.0062	-0.0740	0.2968	-0.0094	0.0293
5	Number of bolls per plant	-0.0513	-0.0171	0.0934	0.0256	0.1352	-0.0006	-0.0020	-0.0460	-0.0084	-0.0348	0.0495
6	Boll Weight (g)	-0.0314	0.2033	0.3478	-0.4019	0.0028	-0.6203	0.2306	0.0282	-0.2154	-0.0406	-0.0597
7	Ginning percentage (%)	-0.2279	-0.3166	-0.2013	-0.0038	0.0074	0.1810	-0.4870	0.0520	-0.0329	0.1392	-0.1266
8	Uniformity Ratio (%)	0.0198	0.0050	-0.0334	-0.0122	-0.0437	-0.0058	-0.0137	0.1285	0.0676	0.1029	-0.0748
9	Fiber Strength (g/tex)	0.1355	-0.0038	-0.0453	0.1372	-0.0224	0.1254	0.0244	0.1899	0.3610	0.2526	-0.0824
10	Upper Half Mean Length (mm)	-0.1358	0.0221	0.1713	0.0089	0.1893	-0.0482	0.2105	-0.5897	-0.5153	-0.7365	0.4286
11	Micronaire ($\mu\text{g}/\text{inch}$)	-0.0029	0.0025	0.0020	0.0004	0.0041	0.0011	0.0029	-0.0065	-0.0026	-0.0065	0.0112
12	Seed cotton yield per plant (gm)	-0.4209	-0.2949	0.1569	0.5428	0.4896	0.2458	-0.3127	-0.3436	-0.1119	-0.3481	0.1563

R SQUORE = 0.814 RESIDUEL EFFECTS = 0.431

Table 4 : Phenotypic path coefficient analysis for morphological, yield contributing and fibre characters in cotton

Sr no.	Characters	Days to 50 % flowering	Number of monopodia	Number of Sympodia	Plant height (cm)	Number of bolls/plant	Boll Weight (g)	Ginning percentage (%)	Uniformity Ratio (%)	Fiber Strength (g/tex)	Upper Half Mean Length (mm)	Micronaire ($\mu\text{g}/\text{inch}$)
1	Days to 50 % flowering	-0.1852	0.0330	0.0109	-0.0002	0.0495	-0.0051	-0.0373	-0.02962	-0.0643	-0.0284	0.0264
2	Number of monopodia	0.0126	-0.0709	0.0047	-0.0007	0.0092	0.0082	-0.0126	-0.01504	0.0003	0.0033	-0.0129
3	Number of Sympodia	-0.0009	-0.0010	0.0156	-0.0025	0.0091	-0.0059	0.0027	0.00096	-0.0011	-0.0031	0.0034
4	Plant height (cm)	0.0004	0.0038	-0.0591	0.3648	0.0579	0.2025	0.0093	-0.08108	0.1369	-0.0036	0.0172

5	Number of bolls/plant	-0.0835	-0.0403	0.1828	0.0496	0.3123	0.0024	-0.0046	-0.08541	-0.0219	-0.0749	0.0885
6	Boll Weight (g)	0.0003	-0.0012	-0.0038	0.0056	0.0001	0.0100	-0.0020	-0.03677	0.0031	0.0007	0.0009
7	Ginning percentage (%)	-0.0484	-0.0427	-0.0422	-0.0061	0.0035	0.0486	-0.2401	-0.01165	-0.0052	0.0359	-0.0034
8	Uniformity Ratio (%)	-0.0136	-0.0063	0.0265	0.0075	0.0374	0.0082	0.0072	-0.1096	-0.0533	-0.0783	0.0463
9	Fiber Strength (g/tex)	-0.0293	-0.0004	-0.0061	0.0316	-0.0059	0.0263	0.0018	-0.03204	0.0843	0.0547	-0.0137
10	Upper Half Mean Length(mm)	-0.0515	0.0156	0.0673	0.0033	0.0807	-0.0225	0.0504	-0.06329	-0.2184	-0.3364	0.1820
11	Micronaire (µg/inch)	0.0361	-0.0459	-0.0559	-0.0119	-0.0716	0.0225	-0.0035	0.03776	0.0412	0.1367	-0.2527
12	Seed cotton yield per plant (gm)	-0.3043	-0.1563	0.1406	0.4409	0.4822	0.2501	-0.2288	-0.3497	-0.0984	-0.2934	0.0821

R SQUQRE = 0.546 RESIDUEL EFFECTS = 0.673

Fig. 1 Genotypic path diagram for seed cotton yield and its attributing characters in cotton

Fig. 2 Phenotypic path diagram for seed cotton yield and its attributing characters in cotton.

Conclusion:

The investigations conducted in this study revealed that traits viz. ; the number of bolls per plant, plant height, boll weight, number of sympodia, ginning percent and fiber fineness are most important traits for effective selection of superior genotypes of *desi* cotton for seed cotton yield and fibre quality parameters. These traits exhibited high heritability, significant positive correlations and substantial direct effects on seed cotton yield. Consequently, they should be prioritized in the selection process when aiming to breed high-performing American cotton varieties.

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*Original not seen.